

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN ABBREVIATIONS AND CLIPPINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract. In English language abbreviation and clippings are different fields of linguistics. This article describes about differences between abbreviations and clippings in English language.

Keywords: word-formation, shortened words, abbreviation, clipping.

The shortening of words means substituting a part for a whole, part of the word is taken away and used for the whole. Ex. demo (demonstration), dub (double), doc (doctor). A shortened word is in some way different from its prototype in usage. The shortened word and its full form have the same lexical meaning differ only in stylistic reference. Ex. exam (colloq), examination (neutral), Chapman (neutral), chap (colloq).

Shortened words are structurally simple words and in most cases have the same lexical meaning as the longer words from which they are derived. We must distinguish lexical abbreviations and clippings.

Abbreviations consist of the first letters of a word, group or a compound word (CPSU, YCL, USA, BBC, NATO) or the component of a two-member group H – (hydrogen) bomb, V – (Victory) day is shortened. The last one is not changed. (1.61)

Abbreviations are words that derived from the first letters of a word, compound or group words. For instance: AIDS (Acquired immune deficiency syndrome), IT (Information technology), UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization), VAT (Value added tax).

Clipping is a derivational way of making new words by reduction. These shortened words are used in sentences like the whole word.

Clipping is a special category of word-making presented by the process of shortening which consists in the reduction of a word to one of its parts. Shortening is a development which has linguistic value of its own in various languages and must not be left unmentioned here as relevant to word-formation in English. Clipping is not so much a method of forming new words as of altering old ones without changing their meaning. (2.102)

Clipping consists in the cutting of one or several syllables of a word. In many cases the stressed syllable is preserved. Ex. Alf from Alfred. (3.203)

Clipping is classified into the following types depending on which part of the word is clipped: a) Words that have been shortened at the end: ad

(advertisement), lab (laboratory), Jap (Japanese), doc (doctor), sis (sister), vac (vacuum-cleaner); b) Words that have been shortened at the beginning: car (motor-car), phone (telephone), cast (broadcast); c) Words in which syllables have been omitted from the middle so called syncope: maths (mathematics), specs (spectacles); d) Words that have been shortened at the beginning and at the end: flu (influenza), tec (detective), frig (refrigerator). (1.61)

Clippings do not always coincide in meaning with the original word. Ex. **doc** and **doctor** have the meaning one who practices medicine, but doctor is also the highest degree given by a university to a scholar or scientist and a person who received such a degree whereas doc is not used with these meanings.(4.48)

Clippings and abbreviations have the some peculiarities as simple words. They take the plural endings and that of the possessive case. They take grammatical inflexions. Ex. exams, docs, cars they are used with articles: the USA, a lab, a vac, a doc etc. they may take derivational affixes: YCL-er, M. P-ess, hanky (from handkerchief), unkie (from uncle).

In conclusion, we should distinguish abbreviations and clippings. Because they are different from each other. Usually they are both used in oral speech. But abbreviations consist of the first letters of a word, group or a compound word, in other words, usually the first letters are taken. In clippings words that have been shortened at the beginning, at the end etc.

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